

ISSUES OF USING COACHING IN PSYCHOLOGICAL SERVICE

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Abstract: In this article, the meaning of coaching, and the methods of using it are discussed in detail. Information is given on how the coaching process can help the client to set goals and clarify, realistically check their needs, and open opportunities and potentials.

Key words: coaching, person, relationship, communication, behavior, opportunity, need, psychological service, client, individuality.

"Psychological service" belongs to the field of educational services and aims to improve the quality and efficiency of personal training and educate a well-rounded person. Psychological service, based on human's behavior and mental activity, age laws of mental development, professional knowledge, characteristics of interaction with peers, students and adults, organization of the educational process, provides opportunities for an individual approach to a person, develops his abilities, determines possible causes of deviations from the norm, ways of psychological-pedagogical correction. With this, the psychological service allows to increase the productivity of the educational system to development a creative and active person, especially in the higher education systems.

Coaching is a technology that helps to create your life as you want it, along with this it allows a person to answer questions, better understand themselves, their desires, aspirations, limit beliefs and fears. If there is a question, then always will be an answer for it. Just like every lock has its own key. Remember the parable about the gods who created the sky, mountains, earth and human intestines. Having created all this, the gods thought about how to hide wisdom and truth from people. Their solution was to hide the truth that people would never think to look at. And they put it inside the person's himself.

If we look at the history of coaching, it is believed that this activity as a special type appeared in the mid-1970s. After that, it was used in business in the

1980s, in sports in the 1990s, then in management, and only then in education. However, at its core, coaching is inextricably linked to learning and development issues.

Our happiness, harmony and resources are within us. The philosophy of coaching is based on this idea. It is important to help a person to look at himself, to listen to the voice of his heart, which contains all the advice.

Coaching process-Goal setting and client clarification. Real check, take a role according to the needs, opportunities, and potential. So you need to build a program and detailed Coaching plan. Having necessary changes with implementation of the plan and obtaining certain results. Monitoring results and providing feedbacks.

Unlike psychotherapy, the essence of coaching is not to study a person, but to set goals and look for ways to achieve them.

Here, the client learns to create opportunities for his own development based on the strengths of his personality. People usually just want to achieve more in life and have the motivation to do so. This is why coaching is sometimes called wellness therapy.

The coach does not decide what is best for the client, because this creates problems for their own decision-making. However, the position of a silent listener is also not suitable for a coach, because his task is to be effective for them. It appears when it is useful for the client and expresses its position. The task of the coach is to help the client understand what needs to be done to achieve the goal and get rid of unnecessary guilt for past actions.

Today, the use of coaching in the psychological service teaches each client to look at his actions through positive intentions, for example, "I wanted the best and I did my best for it." This skill helps the client to know exactly what he wants and how to choose ways to achieve it. It also allows you to understand other people and their behavior.

Coaching is usually conducted in a dialogue format, and the first meeting is always introductory in nature. It defines the request and the objectives. This should be done as accurately as possible to clearly understand whether the work had

results or not. Therefore, the validity of the objective is checked, because sometimes the request is not what the customer is really interested in. Next, he needs to understand what is preventing the client from achieving what he wants and where his responsibility lies in this. In coaching, the situation can be with different colors and stereotypes.

In this case is recommended to use coaching in classroom and extracurricular situations, as well as to be used as part of psychological-pedagogical support of training and professional development. Because through coaching, it is possible to eliminate mental stress in children and increase the mastery rate.

In conclusion, Coaching does not give "valuable advice", but provides the client with real methods and skills, improving people's lives, life experiences, independent learning and personal growth, results-oriented and is a systematic collaborative process. By using coaching in the educational process, in psychological services, it is possible to achieve effective results, such as ensuring the effective exchange of knowledge and the effective development of skills.

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